

applied as a foliar application at booting and 10 d later. We measured ShR incidence as a percentage of tillers affected on 25 randomly selected hills/plot, 20 d after the last spray.

In the first trial, applying gypsum to the soil in two equal splits at different

times was comparable with carbendazim in reducing ShR and increasing grain yield significantly (see table). Foliar application of the salts was inferior to the gypsum application.

In the second trial, all gypsum treatments significantly reduced ShR, al-

though only basal applications increased the yield considerably.

Gypsum is a promising treatment for reducing ShR incidence in rice and for increasing grain yield when applied as two equal splits. ■

Integrated pest management-insects

Effects of botanical treatments on brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)

I. F. Telan, T. H. Xuan, and F. M. Olivares, Jr., Crop Protection Division, Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

We tested several extracts from plant species for use in controlling brown planthopper (BPH).

Field-collected BPH populations were cultured in screenhouse insect cages. Sap was extracted from test botanicals using a mortar and pestle and then mixed with water (1:1). Three-week-old TN1 seedlings/pot (7.6-cm-diam) were kept in a screened enclosure. Leaves were pruned at 30 cm above soil level.

Each extract (4 ml/pot) was applied to rice seedlings using a hand sprayer.

Immediately after treatment, about 900 nymphs (4th-5th stages) and adults (3:1) were released and prorated in the enclosure. We counted BPH on the plants after 12 h.

The free-choice experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design replanted twice for each treatment, and replicated five times. Endosulfan-treated and untreated rice plants served as controls.

Some of the botanical treatments were significantly more effective than others, but none were nearly as effective as endosulfan (see table). Untreated plants had the most insects (8.6/plant). Nymphs and adults responded in the same way to treatments. *Azadirachta indica*, *Anonas reticulata*, and *Tinosphora rumphii* appear to have repellent effects on BPH. ■

Effects of botanical treatments on BPH.

Plant species/ chemical	Plant part used	BPH/ plant ^a (no.)
Endosulfan ^b	-	0.5 a
<i>Anonas reticulata</i>	Leaf	3.6 b
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Leaf	4.0 bc
<i>Tinosphora rumphii</i>	Vine	4.6 bcd
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	Fruit rind	6.0 bcde
<i>Pithosporum resiniferum</i>	Leaf	6.3 bcde
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Leaf	6.5 bcde
<i>Dieffenbachia picta</i>	Leaf, stalk	6.5 bcde
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Leaf, stem	6.5 bcde
<i>Anonas muricata</i>	Leaf	6.8 bcde
<i>Curcuma zedoaria</i>	Rhizome	7.1 bcde
<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Leaf	7.6 de
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Leaf	7.8 de
<i>Anonas squamosa</i>	Leaf	8.1 de
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Leaf	8.6 e
<i>Musa sapientum</i>	Stalk	8.6 e
Control		8.6 e

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bThree tablespoons/16 liters of water.

Research methodology

Illustrating the recommendation domain concept in integrated pest management: an Indian case study

H. M. Singh, Entomology Department, Narendra Deva University for Agriculture and Technology (NDUAT), Kumarganj, Faizabad 224229, Uttar Pradesh, India; R. K. Srivastava, Plant Pathology Department, NDUAT; R. K. Singh, Office of the Director for Research, NDUAT; and S. Savary, Institut Francais de Recherche Scientifique pour le Developpement en Cooperation (ORSTOM)-IRRI Shuttle Project, IRRI

Integrated pest management (IPM) strategies are site-dependent. Among the many reasons for this is that the particular combination of pests and diseases (the injury profile) that affects a given crop is, to a significant extent, driven by location-specific crop management practices. Another reason is that the amount of yield reduction (damage) that can be attributed to a given injury profile depends on the (attainable) yield the crop would have achieved had these pests been absent. The attainable yield reflects a given production situation and is site-

dependent. It is therefore necessary to identify the domains where rice pests and diseases may become constraints to productivity and where differing IPM strategies are to be considered.

Surveys have been jointly initiated by NDUAT, IRRI, and ORSTOM since 1991 to characterize the injury profile associated with differing production situations in Uttar Pradesh, India. The surveys address monsoon season crops in three typical rainfed landforms of two villages. The procedure to analyze this information is exemplified using 1992 data, represent-

ing 80 fields. The data collected cover several categorical (qualitative) or categorized (quantitative) attributes of the agroecosystem as

- components of the cropping practices, such as previous crop in a given field (fallow, wheat, legume, or potato), level of fertilizer inputs (from absent [NPK0] to high [NPK3]), application of manure (yes [man0] or no [man1]), crop establishment method (transplanted [tr] or direct seeded [ds]), water stress (low [WS1] to high [WS3]), and duration of rice crop cycle (short [CD1] to long [CD3]);
- components of the injury profiles, represented by the intensities of disease and pest injuries assessed at three crop development stages, such as maximum proportion of tillers with deadhearts or sheath blight; maximum proportion of panicles with whiteheads, sheath rot, or neck blast; maximum observed number of armyworms/hill; area under the number of observed rice bugs/hill; and area under brown spot intensity or leaffolder injury progress curves; and
- rice yield, estimated from three 1-m² sampling areas in each field (very low, < 2.4 t/ha [Y1] to high, > 3.4 and < 5.2 t/ha [Y4]).

The methodology to analyze these data strongly relies upon nonparametric, multivariate methods that enable the handling of qualitative and quantitative information simultaneously. The analysis proceeds in two steps: (i) patterns of cropping practices are characterized using cluster analysis (Fig. 1), and (ii) these patterns are linked to predominant pests using chi-square tests and correspondence analysis (Fig. 2).

As the crop management practices are described by qualitative attributes, such as variety name, previous crop, crop establishment method, a qualitative metric, such as chi-square distance, is appropriate to aggregate fields into clusters (Fig. 1). Correspondence analysis allows the visualization of relationships among variables. Graphs that can be read as maps are generated. They show the locations of various attributes of the agroecosystem. (See Figure 2 for a path of increasing yield levels corresponding to the changes in

Domain	Cropping practices	Pest constraints
A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High fertilizer input Some manure Previous crop: wheat predominant Transplanted rice Medium-high yield 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadhearts Whiteheads Armyworms Rice bugs Sheath blight Sheath rot Neck blast
B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low fertilizer input Some manure Diverse previous crops Water stress often high Transplanted rice predominant Short cycle Low yield 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Glume discoloration (Leaf blast)
C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low fertilizer input No manure Previous crop:wheat only Medium-low water stress Transplanted or direct seeded rice Long-cycle varieties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weeds above the rice canopy Glume discoloration
D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fertilizer Fallow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadhearts Whiteheads Sheath rot

2. A correspondence analysis of patterns of cropping practices, yield levels, and pest profiles.

crop management practices.) It indicates that recommendation domains associated with the corresponding injury profiles can actually be delineated.

A recommendation domain should be seen in terms of the combination of crop management practices, rather than in terms of spatial proximity, and need not be continuous at the farm level (Fig. 2). For example, two neighboring fields may belong to different recommendation domains.

This approach provides a framework for the current hypothesis-testing process, where the actual damage due to pest combinations is being measured in farmers' field experiments in Uttar Pradesh and in crop loss data base experiments at IRRI. ■

Empirical estimates of yield and pest potentials of farmers' rainfed lowland ricefields

H. O. Pinnschmidt, IRRI; P. Mekwatanakari Ubon Rice Research Center (URRC), P.O. Box 65, Muang, Ubon Ratchathani 34000, Thailand; N. D. Long, University of Agriculture and Forestry (UAF), Thu Duo, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, P. S. Teng, IRRI; J. L. Gaunt, Natural Resources Institute, Chatham Maritime, Chatham, Kent, ME40B. UK; and H. U. Neue, IRRI

Data on crop performance, including disease, insect, weed, and other pest severities; yield; soil conditions; and crop and pest management practices, were collected in field surveys and holistic experiments with integrated crop protection treatments at four rainfed lowland sites in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, and northeast Thailand in 1992. At each site, 4-5 farmers' fields were selected and subdivided into plots receiving either no pest control, pest control according to farmers' practices, or fungicide and insecticide applications 4-5 times during the growing season. Fields were visited repeatedly during the growing season for data collection. Data were used to develop simple methods for estimating yield potentials of sites, pest-yield effects, and pest proneness.

Target yields (Y_t) were computed based on a model developed and parameterized by Neue in 1985: $Y_t = 0.05 FN_e - 0.000225 FN_e^2 + 0.05 FN_e N_t + (2.4152 N_t - 6.0882 N_t^2) d_r$, where N_t = % soil N, d_r = effective rooting depth in cm, and FN_e = effective uptake of N fertilizer in kg/ha: $FN_e = 1.193 FN^{0.9}$, where FN = fertilizer N in kg/ha. N_t was estimated based on total soil C content, assuming a C-N ratio of 10.

Because a portion of the total C and N in soils is effectively inert due to chemical nature and organomineral interactions, the model was modified by a relationship independently found by Gaunt that accounts for protection of soil C and N by clay: $N_t = (C - 0.016L)/10$, where C = % soil carbon and L = % clay content of soil. A variable (GPEST) representing the combined maximum severity levels of pest intensity on